

Bioelectrocatalytic Activity of W-Formate Dehydrogenase Covalently Immobilized on Functionalized Gold and Graphite Electrodes

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Abstract

Decrease of greenhouse gases like CO₂ has become a key challenge for human kind and the study of the electrocatalytic properties of CO₂-reducing enzymes such as formate dehydrogenases is of importance for this goal. In this work we study the covalent bonding of *Desulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough FdhAB formate dehydrogenase to chemically modified gold and low-density graphite electrodes, using electrostatic interactions for favoring oriented immobilization of the enzyme. Electrochemical measurements show both bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of formate and reduction of CO₂ by direct electron transfer. Atomic force microscopy and quartz crystal microbalance characterization, as well as comparison of direct and mediated electrocatalysis, suggest that a compact layer of formate dehydrogenase was anchored to the electrode surface with some crosslinked aggregates. Furthermore, operational stability for CO₂ electroreduction to formate by direct electron transfer is shown with approximately 100% faradaic yield.

Keywords: carbon dioxide reduction, formate dehydrogenase, bioelectrocatalysis, oriented immobilization, metalloenzymes

1. Introduction

The increase of CO₂ atmospheric concentration plays a major role in climate change and global warming. The greenhouse effects caused by current emissions may be irreversible for at least 1.000 years after such emissions stop.¹ A negative emissions' balance that reduces the amount of CO₂ is one of the most important challenges ever faced by human kind. CO₂ has an intrinsic kinetic inertia and high thermodynamic stability making it difficult to either trap or reduce. Formic acid/formate is a stable product that can be obtained by bi-electronic reduction of CO₂ (equation 1). It has several advantages because it is liquid at standard temperature, it is a good energy vector that can be stored easily and then employed in different energy processes such as fuel cells or in synthesis of chemicals.²

Electrochemical reduction of CO₂ has been demonstrated but it requires applying a very high overpotential that implies low selectivity, low catalytic yield and a lack of specificity.³ Interestingly, formate dehydrogenases (FDH) are redox enzymes that specifically catalyze the reduction of CO₂ to formate in a reversible way. Therefore, their study as bioelectrocatalysts is of importance as source of inspiration for obtaining more efficient and sustainable biomimetic catalysts for CO₂ reduction. There are two types of FDH enzymes: the first type is formed by NAD⁺-dependent FDHs, which are present in plants, fungi and some aerobic bacteria; these FDHs are mostly biased towards formate oxidation.⁴ The second type comprises Mo- and W-dependent FDHs, which are present in anaerobic prokaryotes and have shown high efficiency for reducing CO₂ to formate with high turnover values. In order to function *in vitro*, these FDHs

require strict anaerobic conditions and an initial activation by reduction, which are the conditions for the enzyme to function *in vivo*.⁵⁻⁷ This kind of FDHs are able to catalyze CO₂ reduction with low redox overpotential, close to the thermodynamic value ($E^{\circ} = -0.42$ V vs SHE). Specifically, W-FDH enzymes, due to the lower potential of their active site, seem the best candidates for catalyzing CO₂ reduction.⁸ Several studies have been performed to elucidate the catalytic mechanism of FDHs.⁹⁻¹² Recently, Oliveira *et al.* reported an efficient system to produce recombinant a W-containing FDH from *Desulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough (*DvH*-FDH), which is a heterodimer that consists of two subunits with molecular masses of 110 and 24 kDa, respectively. The active center of tungsten is located in the large subunit (Fig. 1A) and it is responsible of the reversible conversion between carbon dioxide and formate according to equation (1). The crystallographic structure model shows that the enzyme surface has a heterogeneous distribution of charges, in which the formate entrance site is positively charged, while the redox donor/acceptor binding site (containing a Fe₄S₄ cluster) is negatively charged. Another three Fe₄S₄ clusters within the protein structure form the electron transfer path to the W-active site. Interestingly, the enzyme can be stably isolated in aerobic conditions and has a high catalytic turnover for CO₂ reduction of 315 ± 28 s⁻¹ using excess of reduced methyl viologen as reductant. It was also shown that 5 min pre-incubation of the *DvH*-FDH with 50 mM dithiothreitol was enough to observe full catalytic activity.¹³

These interesting biochemical properties of *DvH*-FDH have spurred bioelectrocatalytic studies of CO₂ reduction focusing on building interfaces for improving the rate of charge exchange between electrodes and the enzyme's W active site. Miller *et al.* described the adsorption of *DvH*-FDH to metal oxides electrodes with fast direct electron transfer (DET) across the enzyme-metal interface.¹⁴ Szczesny *et al.*

fabricated a gas diffusion electrode modified with polymer/enzyme layers for electroenzymatic CO₂ reduction in which the low potential redox mediator was covalently bound to the polymer. This configuration avoided the disadvantages of using a redox mediator in solution.¹⁵

In the present work we study different approaches to modify gold and low-density graphite electrodes in order to place amino groups on their exposed surface. These functionalities allow for covalent anchoring of *DvH*-FDH with an orientation modulated by electrostatic interactions to favor DET with the electrode while maintaining operational stability. Both formate oxidation and CO₂ reduction electrocatalytic properties of the immobilized *DvH*-FDH have been studied, and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM) characterization allowed correlating the modified electrodes conformation with their catalytic function.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Reagents

All used chemicals and materials were purchased from commercial suppliers and employed with any further purification. 4-aminothiophenol (4-ATP) 97%, 6-mercapto-1-hexanol (MH) 97%, p-nitrophenyldiazonium tetrafluoroborate salt 97%, *N*-Ethyl-*N'*-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC), *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) (97%), DL-dithiothreitol (DTT), glutaraldehyde (25%), sodium hydrogen carbonate, sodium formate > 99%, methyl viologen dichloride hydrate (MV) 98%, benzyl viologen dichloride hydrate (BV) 97%, potassium cyanide (99%), potassium chloride ultrapure, ethanol absolute grade, phosphoric acid 99%, citric acid 99%, sodium citrate 99%, sodium hydroxide 99%, sulfuric acid > 95%, MES 99.5%, tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris-HCl), sodium tetrahydroborate and tetrabutylammonium fluoride > 99%, acetonitrile, low density graphite (LDG) (99.9%),

3mm diameter) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck). MicroPolish alumina suspensions was purchased from Buehler. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate 99%, hydrogen peroxide 30%, sodium hydrogen phosphate 99% and Amicon Ultra-0.5 Centrifugal Filter Unit Ultracel-50 regenerated cellulose membrane, 0.5 mL sample volume were obtained from Merck. Sodium nitrate was obtained from Panreac and glycerol 10% from Scharlau.

All solutions were prepared with Milli-Q grade water (18.2 M Ω ·cm, Millipore) and purged with 99.99 % N₂ (Air Liquide) during 10 minutes before any further use.

2.2 Enzyme

The recombinant tungsten-dependent FdhAB formate dehydrogenase from *Desulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough (*DvH*-FDH) was isolated and purified as previously described.¹³ 33.7 μ M stock solutions, with a turnover of 1144 s⁻¹ for formate oxidation with 2 mM BV and of 236 s⁻¹ for CO₂ reduction with 1 mM MV⁺, were stored at -80 °C in a buffer solution containing 20 mM Tris-HCl, 10% glycerol, 10 mM NaNO₃ at pH 7.6. Prior to a set of measurements, the buffer was exchanged to 10 mM MES at pH 6 by ultrafiltration with 50 kDa centrifugal filters and the enzyme was stored in aliquots of 6 μ l containing *DvH*-FDH 27 μ M at -80 °C.

2.3 Preparation of Gold and Graphite Electrodes

Disk electrodes of polycrystalline gold with 0.5 cm diameter (Pine Instruments) were cleaned by immersion in freshly prepared *piranha* solution (3:1 H₂SO₄:H₂O₂) (*caution: this is a very exothermic and hazardous solution*) for 10 minutes and further rinsed with MilliQ water. Afterwards, the electrodes were polished successively with alumina suspensions of 1, 0.3 and 0.05 μ m in diameter respectively and sonicated for 10 minutes in a H₂O: EtOH mixture (1:1) to remove alumina traces from the surface. The gold electrode surfaces were then electrochemically cleaned using two processes of

cyclic voltammetry. In the first one 15 cycles were performed between 0 V and -1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (3M Cl⁻) at 0.2 V/s scan rate in 0.5 M NaOH electrolyte solution. In the second step 20 cycles between 0 V and +1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (3M Cl⁻) at 0.2 V/s in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ were applied. The electroactive area of the electrodes was calculated as described by Trasatti *et al.*¹⁶, resulting in an average roughness of 1.1 ± 0.3 .

LDG rods of 0.3 cm diameter were also used as working electrodes. One edge of each rod was polished during 60 s with emery sand paper, rinsed with MilliQ water and then sonicated for 10 minutes in H₂O. Finally, the clean electrodes were left to dry for 12 h at room temperature before use. The rods sides were covered with Teflon band so that the geometric area of the LDG exposed to the solution was 0.07 cm². The graphite rods were then fitted into a custom-built plastic adaptor screwed to a Pine Instruments rotating electrode system.

2.4 Chemical modification of the electrode surfaces.

Two different approaches have been used to modify the electrodes' surfaces in order to expose positively amino groups for further covalent immobilization of DvH-FDH. In the first approach the clean gold electrodes surface was modified with a thiol self-assembled monolayer (SAM) of 4-ATP as we previously reported.¹⁷ In the second approach the clean gold or LDG electrodes, were electrochemically modified with 4-nitrophenyl radicals obtained by the electrochemical reduction of p-nitrophenyldiazonium tetrafluoroborate salt. This procedure was respectively done as previously reported for LDG¹⁸ and gold¹⁹ electrodes. Only in the case of gold electrodes the non-modified regions were blocked with self-assembled MH molecules.²⁰

2.5 Covalent immobilization of formate dehydrogenase on electrodes surfaces.

20 μ L of 8.1 μ M DvH-FDH solution in 10 mM MES pH 6.0 buffer was placed on the modified electrodes' surface and incubated for 30 minutes to allow enzyme

molecules rearrangement to yield an oriented binding through dipole moment-driven electrostatic interactions. Afterwards 20 μl of a 10 mM MES pH 6.0 buffer solution containing 7.7 mM of EDC and 9.5 mM of NHS was added on top during 90 minutes for covalent attachment of *DvH*-FDH to the amino groups of the electrode surface. After that, the modified electrodes were rinsed by immersing them several times in 10 mM MES solution at pH 6.0. Finally, the immobilized *DvH*-FDH was activated inside the glovebox by incubating the enzymatic electrodes for 5 minutes in a 10 mM MES solution at pH 6.0 containing 50 mM DTT. This procedure has demonstrated to increase the activity of the enzyme.¹³ Prior to any electrochemical measurement the electrodes were washed again by immersing them several times in 10 mM MES solution at pH 6.0.

Additional glutaraldehyde cross-linking of FDH was also tested as follows: after activation with DTT the modified electrodes were incubated for either 30 or 60 minutes in a 0.9% glutaraldehyde solution in 10 mM MES solution at pH 6.0. Finally, the electrodes were rinsed as described before.

2.6 Electrochemical measurements

All electrochemical measurements were carried with an Autolab PGTAT30 potentiostat controlled by GPES 4.9 software (Eco Chemie, The Netherlands). All electrochemical experiments involving the FDH were performed inside a MBraun glovebox with an oxygen content lower than 0.1 ppm. Cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry were conducted in a three-electrode glass cell at 25 ± 1 °C thermostated with a circulating water jacket. Either polycrystalline gold disk or LDG rods were employed as working electrodes, while a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and a flame-annealed platinum wire were used as a reference and counter electrodes respectively. All potentials are given respect to SHE ($E_{\text{SHE}} = E_{\text{SCE}} + 0.241$ V). The electrolyte volume in the experiments was 33 mL. Prior to any electrochemical

measurements, any possible traces of oxygen in the solutions was removed inside the glovebox by bubbling N₂ (99.999%) during 20 minutes and flow of the inert gas was kept over the working solution during the measurements. All given current densities were calculated using the geometric surface of the working electrode that was exposed to the electrolyte solution. The cyclic voltammograms shown in the manuscript correspond to typical results obtained under the same experimental conditions.

2.7 Formate quantification

Production of formate by the *DvH*-FDH cathode during chronoamperometric measurements was quantified by ionic chromatography-conductivity detector (Metrosep A Supp 7–250 × 4.0 mm column) in a Metrohm 883 Basic IC Plus using 3.6 mM sodium carbonate in water as the eluent (0.6 mL/min). The chromatograph was also equipped with a Metrohm Suppressor Module (MSM) with 250 mM H₂SO₄ and 100 mM oxalic acid as the regenerating solution and 5 % acetone in Type 1 water as the rinsing solution. The calibration curve was carried out in the electrolyte cell conditions and the formate was identified by the presence of the peak at the retention time of 8.206 min after ultrafiltration through a 0.22 μm regenerated cellulose (RC) filter.

2.8 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) measurements

Gold-coated slides from Arrandee Metal GmbH were first cleaned during 10 minutes in piranha solution and later flame-annealed in order to obtain large and well-ordered Au(111) terraces. Immobilization of *DvH*-FDH was carried out as described above for the polycrystalline gold electrodes.

Tapping mode AFM images were recorded with an Atomic Force Microscope from Agilent Technologies 5500 with the substrate immersed in the same electrolyte in which the electrochemical measurements were done. All images were recorded at room temperature using silicon nitrile cantilevers with a nominal spring constant of 0.72 N/m

and a resonance frequency of 70 KHz (Olympus OMCL-RC). A PicoView 1.3 (Agilent Technologies) and WSxM 5.0 Develop 8.0 (NanoTech) were employed for data acquisition and analysis, respectively.

2.9 Quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) measurements

A QCM able to monitor both frequency and dissipation changes (KSV QCM-Z500) was employed to quantify the amount of *DvH*-FDH covalently bound to a gold substrate modified with a SAM of 4-ATP. Frequency change (Δf) was directly transformed into surface-adsorbed mass using the Sauerbrey equation.²¹ Previous to each experiment, gold coated QCM crystal sensors with 5 MHz fundamental resonance frequency (Qsense QSX 301) were properly cleaned and activated. Gold substrates were cleaned with a piranha solution for 5 minutes, rinsed with MilliQ water, and dried under nitrogen prior to the formation of a thiol self-assembled monolayer (SAM) by exposing the surface to a 1 mM solution of 4-ATP in ethanol overnight at room temperature. Finally, gold substrates were rinsed with ETOH and then with MilliQ water. After that, the modified QCM crystal was immersed in a 10 mM MES solution pH 6 during 1 hour to protonate the amino group on the surface, and finally was dried under nitrogen before mounting in the QCM chamber. All measurements were performed at operating frequency of 35 MHz (i.e. seventh overtone), with a continuous flow rate of 50 μ l/min, and fixed temperature of 25 °C.

3. Results

3.1 Covalent immobilization of *DvH*-FDH on gold substrates

Two types of gold surface modifications were tested in order to expose amino groups. Positively charged amino groups on the surface should allow electrostatic orientation of *DvH*-FDH molecules upon their deposition with the negatively charged region surrounding the most exposed Fe₄S₄ cluster facing the electrode (Fig. 1A). In the

first method a 4-ATP SAM monolayer is formed on the gold surface, allowing the formation of amide bonds with the enzyme's carboxylic residues surrounding the exposed Fe_4S_4 cluster (Fig. 1B). In the second method the aminophenyl (AP) groups on the gold surface are formed by electrochemical reduction of a diazonium salt derivative, and subsequently the non-modified gold regions are blocked by self-assembling of MH (Fig. 1 C).

Figure 1. (A) Representation of the crystallographic structure of *DvH-FDH* with its exposed Fe_4S_4 cluster. Covalent immobilization of *DvH-FDH* on modified gold electrodes with a (B) 4-ATP SAM and (C) a mixed AP+MH layer. In B) and C) the electrostatic potential mapping of the protein surface is shown. Reprinted in part with permission from reference 13. Copyright 2020 American Chemical Society.

The enzyme-modified gold surfaces were imaged with AFM. Fig. 2 shows images corresponding to *DvH*-FDH immobilized on different monolayers, one with a 4-ATP SAM (A) and the other one with a mixed AP+MH layer (B). The presence of the covalently bound *DvH*-FDH changed the appearance of the gold surface. Control images of the surfaces without enzyme are shown in Fig S1, comprising the bare clean gold, the gold covered with a 4-ATP monolayer and the gold covered with AP, as well as the gold covered with the AP+MH mixed layer. Without the enzyme, the roughness is below 5 nm and the grooves separating the terraces are well defined. The aggregates decorating the edges of the monolayer with 4-ATP are possibly due to a preference of the molecules to adsorb on the more reactive edges of the gold terraces, as has been previously described.²² In contrast, the gold terraces modified with the enzyme show an increased roughness, while the clefts between them were smoothed, compatible with protein molecules being deposited inside the grooves (Fig. 2). Qualitatively, the appearance is that of a compact protein layer with the presence of some higher protuberances of 20 nm, which could correspond to a few protein molecules aggregated (Fig. S2).

Figure 2. AFM topography images of *DvH*-FDH covalently immobilized to gold substrates modified with A) 4-ATP SAM and B) mixed AP+MH layer. C, D) Cross-sectional domain of A and B, respectively.

In order to quantify the amount of protein attached using this immobilization protocol we proceeded to perform QCM experiments. This technique allows associating the changes in the resonance frequency of a piezoelectric quartz crystal to the amount of mass deposited on its surface. We modified the gold surface on the quartz crystal with a 4-ATP monolayer, immersed it during 1h into a pH 6 10 mM MES solution to protonate the amino groups and placed it on the equipment. Afterwards we monitored the changes in the resonance frequency as we flowed over the surface different solutions. Fig. 3 shows the changes in the frequency (left axis) and in the dissipation (right axis) registered as a function of time. Black arrows show the time at which each solution was injected into the measuring chamber. Flowing a 10 mM MES buffer pH 6.0 solution containing 1 μ M of *DvH*-FDH during approximately 30 minutes yielded a 66 Hz change in the signal. Then we substituted the solution by 10 mM MES pH 6.0 buffer containing 7.7 mM of EDC and 9.5 mM of NHS instead of the enzyme, aiming to activate the formation of the covalent link between the exposed carboxylic groups of the enzyme and the amino groups available in the 4-ATP SAM. The 10 Hz increase of the frequency could be due to slight changes in the viscosity of the medium or to a small release of adsorbed enzyme. Afterwards we injected again *DvH*-FDH fresh solution to check if the activation induced further crosslinking between the flowing enzyme and the FDH attached to the surface. We observed a reversible decrease of only a few Hz, which increased again when the surface was rinsed with a buffer solution. This sensogram indicates that the enzyme covalently attached to the surface was the one adsorbed initially due to the electrostatic interaction between the negatively charged

carboxyl groups of *DvH*-FDH and the positively charged amino groups on the surface. Addition of EDC stabilized the enzyme layer to further rinsing. The changes in the dissipation during the whole process remained below 1×10^{-6} , indicating that the material adsorbed to the surface was firmly packed and therefore the Sauerbrey equation can be used to associate the frequency changes observed to the mass of enzyme deposited on the surface. This calculation determines that the enzyme coverage was $(8.6 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-12} \text{ mol} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Figure 3: QCM frequency (solid green line) and dissipation (solid blue line) response (seventh overtone) for the covalent immobilization process of *DvH*-FDH on gold substrates modified with 4-ATP SAM.

3.2 Bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of formate to carbon dioxide with the modified gold electrodes

Both the AFM and QCM measurements confirmed that *DvH*-FDH was covalently anchored to the gold substrates. In order to verify that the immobilized enzyme retained its catalytic activity and also was oriented with its exposed redox center close to the gold surface, we studied the bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of formate to CO_2 by direct

electron transfer (DET) for both surface modification strategies. However, these two strategies did not allow studying the reverse activity of CO₂ reduction to formate because the reductive desorption of assembled thiols starts at -0.39 V vs SHE in pH 7.6 phosphate buffer (Fig. S3), which is higher than the thermodynamic value for reduction of CO₂.²³

Figure 4. Bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of 20 mM formate in 0.1 M phosphate, pH 7.6 buffer measured for *DvH*-FDH covalently immobilized on gold electrodes modified

with 4-ATP SAM. (A) Consecutive voltammetry cycles in DET regime during 30 min (black solid lines, a-c); the dashed black (d) and red (e) voltammograms correspond to the control electrodes without immobilized enzyme and without formate respectively. (B) Comparison of MET and DET-based bioelectrocatalysis: cyclic voltammograms in presence (solid blue line, a) and absence (black solid line, b) of 0.16 mM benzyl viologen; the dashed blue voltammogram (c) corresponds to the control electrode without immobilized enzyme and in presence of 0.16 mM benzyl viologen. Scan rate was 0.01 V s^{-1} and temperature was 25°C .

Figure 4 shows the electrochemical response of *DvH*-FDH covalently bound to gold electrodes modified with 4-ATP SAM amino groups in presence of 20 mM formate. Cyclic voltammograms in absence of redox mediator were recorded during 30 minutes for measuring the oxidation of formate at the Au/4-ATP/FDH electrode by DET regime (Fig. 4A, a-c). It can be observed that the electroactivity of *DvH*-FDH gradually decreased with the successive cycles. However, comparison with the voltammograms of the control electrodes lacking either FDH (Fig 4A, d) or formate (Fig 4A, e) indicates that the signal loss is only 15% (at the most positive potential) after 30 minutes of sweeping. This result suggests either partial enzyme desorption, inhibition or denaturation with time. The onset of the electrocatalytic current is at -0.410 V , which is approximately at the thermodynamic value of the $\text{CO}_2/\text{formate}$ pair and in agreement with a reversible catalyst immobilized on the electrode.²³ Furthermore, the shape of the catalytic wave that does not reach a plateau and increases almost linearly with the overpotential is typical of protein film voltammetry rate-limited by the DET step.^{14,17,23,24}

In order to reveal the full electroactivity of the enzyme molecules immobilized on the electrode we added the redox mediator benzyl viologen to the solution. In this case,

mediated electron transfer (MET) bioelectrocatalysis led to a sigmoidal cyclic voltammogram reaching a current plateau at just 0.1 V overpotential. Moreover, the MET-based catalytic current was approximately 3 times larger than the DET-based one at the highest overpotential measured (Fig. 4B, a). These characteristics of the cyclic voltammogram under quiescent conditions clearly suggest an electrocatalytic process rate-limited by the enzymatic reaction.²⁴

On the other hand, when *DvH*-FDH was immobilized on a gold electrode modified with a mixed AP+MH layer the DET-based electrocatalytic current was almost negligible and only observed at very high overpotential (Fig. 5, a-b inset). This result clearly demonstrates that the DET between the enzyme and the electrode is inefficient when *DvH*-FDH is covalently bound to the mixed AP+MH layer. Nevertheless, a clear MET-based electrocatalytic process was observed in presence of benzyl viologen in solution, although the catalytic plateau current (approximately $30 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, Fig. 5) was 4 times lower in comparison with the result obtained by immobilization of the enzyme on the 4-ATP SAM (approximately $120 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, Fig. 4B, a). By increasing the amount of *DvH*-FDH during the immobilization onto the gold electrode modified with the mixed AP+MH layer the MET-based bioelectrocatalytic plateau current increased, although the DET-based process did not improve (Fig. S4). Thus, we discard this immobilization method as a valid one for optimizing DET of *DvH*-FDH on gold, most probably because it does not lead to a correct orientation of the W-FDH with its most exposed 4Fe4S cluster near the electrode surface.

Figure 5. Bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of 20 mM formate 0.1 M phosphate, pH 7.6 buffer measured for *DvH*-FDH covalently immobilized on gold electrodes modified with mixed AP+MH layer. Cyclic voltammograms measured in absence (solid grey lines, a-b) and in presence (solid blue line, d) of 0.16 mM BV. The dashed black, c, and blue, e, voltammograms correspond to the control electrode without immobilized enzyme in absence and in presence of the redox mediator, respectively. Scan rate was 0.01 V s^{-1} and temperature was 25°C . Inset: magnification of the cyclic voltammograms in absence of BV.

3.3 Bioelectrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide to formate with graphite electrodes

DvH-FDH is an ideal model system for electrocatalytic studies of CO_2 reduction because it has been found the most active enzyme for this process.¹³ As we indicated above, the negative potentials needed for CO_2 reduction are not compatible with the stability of thiols' SAM used for the covalent immobilization of the enzyme on gold electrodes. Aiming to overcome this limitation we have developed a strategy for covalent bonding of the *DvH*-FDH that allows reaching the necessary negative

potentials. The functionalization of LDG electrodes with an AP layer by diazonium reduction is a valid alternative because it avoids the incorporation of the MH SAM required to prevent the enzyme denaturalization that occurs on bare gold. First, we verified that this method led to the immobilization of *DvH*-FDH in an oriented fashion that allows the electrocatalytic activity for formate reduction by DET. Figure S5 shows that the measured catalytic currents for formate oxidation, with just 0.1 V of overpotential, are higher with modified LDG electrodes, either in the DET ($322 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) or MET ($1180 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) regime, compared to gold electrodes. This can be attributed to the much higher porosity of the LDG electrodes that allows a higher loading of immobilized enzyme.²⁵ The cyclic voltammogram recorded in presence of the substrate under MET regime yielded a peaked shape instead of the sigmoidal shape expected for an electrocatalytic process. This effect is attributed to the high catalytic current, which leads to mass transfer limitation towards the electrode surface in quiescent solution. Indeed, increase of the mass transport rate of substrate and redox mediator by electrode rotation led to a significant increase of the catalytic current (Fig. S6). On the other hand, the DET-based electrocatalytic current barely increased upon electrode rotation, confirming that in that case interfacial electron transfer from the immobilized *DvH*-FDH to the electrode was the rate-limiting step.

Once it was checked that the *DvH*-FDH covalently immobilized on LDG electrodes was active for formate oxidation, the reverse reaction of CO₂ reduction was studied. As the CO₂ reduction activity of formate dehydrogenases is considerably lower than the formate oxidation one,^{6,13} we doubled the amount of enzyme during the immobilization step. Figure 6 shows the cyclic voltammograms of the LDG/AP/FDH electrode in a pH 6.0 citrate buffer solution containing 50 mM NaHCO₃ to obtain an excess of dissolved CO₂ that does not limit the enzyme kinetics.^{13,23} Under the DET regime the cyclic

voltammograms in Figure 6A show the immobilized *DvH*-FDH catalyzing the interconversion between CO₂ and formate, which was generated at the electrode surface at the lower potentials, close to the thermodynamic potential. Moreover, the peaked shape of the cyclic voltammogram was probably due to depletion of formate at the electrode surroundings when higher potentials caused *DvH*-FDH formate-oxidizing activity. Under MET regime in presence of methyl viologen (Fig. 4 B) the enzyme activity increased 3-fold, in agreement with the experiments performed in presence of formate (Fig. S5).

Figure 6. Bioelectrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ measured for *DvH*-FDH covalently immobilized on a LDG/AP electrode in 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 6.0 containing 50 mM NaHCO₃. Cyclic voltammograms in (A) DET and (B) MET regime (0.16 mM methyl viologen) before (green solid lines, c) and after (black solid lines, a) addition of 50 mM NaHCO₃. The CVs of the control electrodes without immobilized *DvH*-FDH and in presence of 50 mM NaHCO₃ are shown as red lines, b. The scan rate was 0.01 V s⁻¹ and the temperature was 25 °C.

The operational stability of the FHD immobilized on LDG electrode for electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction by DET was studied by chronoamperometry at -0.66 V vs SHE (Fig. 7). After the addition of 50 mM sodium bicarbonate the current density reached a value of -200 μA cm⁻². The catalytic current density decreased gradually with time, although the electrode showed an operational stability of approximately 90 min, at which 34% of the initial catalytic current was maintained (Fig. 7). Integration of the total charge produced during several chronamperometric measurements allowed estimating the concentration of produced formate assuming a 100% faradaic yield of the bioelectrocatalytic process. The average value from 3 measurements done with different *DvH*-FDH-LDG electrodes was 3.3 ± 0.4 μM. The negative control measurement was

done by a previous immersion of the *DvH*-FDH-LDG electrode in 2 M HCl for 5 min in order to denature the enzyme, which was then thoroughly washed in 10 mM MES, pH 6.0 buffer before measuring the chronoamperometry in presence of 50 mM Na₂CO₃. The chronoamperometry obtained with the denatured electrode yielded the background current signal (Fig. S7).

Figure 7. Chronoamperometry at -0.66 V vs SHE under stirring with a LDG/AP/FDH electrode in presence of 50 mM NaHCO₃ in 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 6.0 and 25 °C. The red arrow indicates substrate addition and the dashed blue line represents the projection of the background current in absence of substrate for integrating the charge of the catalytic process.

We studied the effect of crosslinking the enzymes using 0.9% glutaraldehyde after the covalent immobilization on LDG electrodes with the aim of increasing the operational stability for the bioelectrocatalytic reduction of CO₂. The crosslinking with glutaraldehyde during 60 minutes caused a remarkable decrease in the activity of the enzyme, as the electrocatalytic current was reduced more than 50%. The crosslinking during 30 minutes increased the stability of the immobilized DVH-FDH, improving the operational time up to approximately 3.5 h (Fig. S8). However, the calculated amount of

CO₂ reduced to formate from the chronoamperometric measurement was similar to the measurements performed without crosslinking the enzyme (Table S1), due to the initial decrease of the electrocatalytic current caused by such crosslinking process. For that reason, the crosslinking step with glutaraldehyde was forsaken.

Figure 8. Quantification by ionic chromatography of formate concentration produced with a LDG-AP-FDH electrode during typical chronoamperometries at -0.66 V vs SHE under stirring in presence of 50 mM NaHCO₃ in 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 6.0 and 25 °C. The black circles correspond to the formate calibration plot and the red open red circles correspond to the three electrolyte samples taken from the chronoamperometric measurement.

Formate production was also quantified by ionic chromatography. The calibration used for formate determination by ionic chromatography and the values for 3 replicates from chronoamperometric measurements are shown in Fig. 8. The average concentration of formate produced after 90 min of chronoamperometry was 3.7 ± 0.5 μM , a very similar value to that estimated from charge integration taking into account the experimental error.

4. Discussion

In this work we have studied two different strategies aimed to obtain oriented covalent immobilization of *DvH*-FDH on either gold or graphite electrodes with its most exposed redox site facing the electrode surface. Even if the thiol-modified gold electrode strategy only allows studying the formate oxidation activity of *DvH*-FDH and not the CO₂ reduction one, it has the advantage of allowing the characterization of the modified electrode by AFM and QCM. Therefore, the FDH-modified electrode conformation can be correlated with its catalytic function.

Both the formation of a 4-ATP SAM over gold and the functionalization of LDG with aminophenyl groups by electrochemical reduction of a diazonium derivative have been suitable for measuring high electrocatalytic currents of formate oxidation by DET. The results are comparable to those previously reported using the same strategies for *D. gigas* NiFe-hydrogenase, which has a similar charge distribution in the protein surface.^{17,26} Therefore, we confirm that electrostatic interactions between the positively charged amino groups on the electrode surface and the negatively charged amino acid residues surrounding the most exposed Fe₄S₄ cluster modulate the orientation of an enzyme monolayer previous to the covalent immobilization step. However, a distinctive behavior is observed for the immobilized *DvH*-FDH when a redox mediator is added to the solution. The MET-based electrocatalytic current densities increased 3-4 times the DET-based ones (depending on the overpotential at which they are measured) with both Au/4-ATP and LDG/AP electrodes, whereas in our previous works of oriented covalent immobilization of hydrogenases and laccases on electrodes the addition of redox mediator in solution seldom increased the DET-based electrocatalytic currents.^{26,19} The AFM and QCM characterization performed in the present work for the *DvH*-FDH covalently bound to Au/4-ATP electrodes provides an explanation for this discrepancy.

The AFM images suggest a compact layer of protein attached to the modified-gold surface including numerous aggregates with heights of 15-20 nm, which can be assigned to 2 or 3 crosslinked enzyme molecules. In contrast, topographic profiles obtained from AFM images of *D. gigas* NiFe-hydrogenase,¹⁷ *D. vulgaris* NiFeSe-hydrogenase (*DvH-Hase*)²⁷ and *Trametes hirsuta* laccase¹⁹ covalently bound on functionalized gold surfaces were compatible with a more spaced monolayer of attached enzyme molecules. The QCM study of the *DvH*-FDH covalent binding to Au/4-ATP has allowed determining the enzyme coverage, $(8.6 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-12}$ mol cm⁻², which is approximately 2 to 3 times higher than the value expected for a spaced monolayer of an enzyme of this dimension. Therefore, both QCM and AFM measurements point to the presence of crosslinked enzyme molecules on top of the monolayer directly bound to the surface, which are too far to participate on DET with the electrode but are capable of MET-based electrocatalysis. Indeed, the crystal structures of *DvH*-FDH¹³ and *DvH*-Hase²⁸ indicate a much higher amount of lysine residues in the protein surface of the former than in the latter, which could favor crosslinking during the carbodiimide coupling step of the immobilization process.

The bioelectrocatalytic currents measured of formate oxidation, either by DET or MET, are much higher when the *DvH*-FDH was covalently immobilized to the LDG/AP electrodes than to the Au/4-ATP. These results are not surprising as the electroactive area of the former, a highly porous material,²⁵ is much larger than that of planar gold. Thus, a higher coverage of immobilized enzyme per geometric surface of electrode is expected in the first case. For technical reasons we could not directly determine the enzyme loading on LDG electrodes by QCM, although we can estimate this value from the ratio between the two types of electrodes of plateau currents obtained in presence of BV as redox mediator. Under these conditions the enzymatic reaction rate limits the

electrocatalytic process and we can assume that the current density value is proportional to the total amount of enzyme immobilized, as in both cases it is covalently bound by the same chemical reaction. In this way, we can estimate an enzyme coverage of 1.06×10^{-10} mol cm⁻² on the modified LDG electrodes.

The covalent immobilization of DvH-FDH to LDG/AP electrodes allowed measuring also the electrocatalytic currents due to the reverse activity of CO₂ reduction, which is of more interest from the technological point of view. In similar way to the formate oxidation electroactivity, the MET-based electrocatalytic current was significantly higher than the DET-based one. For comparison of data obtained with electrodes with different electroactive areas and enzyme loadings, it is useful to calculate the apparent catalytic rate ($k_{cat\ app}$) of the immobilized enzyme normalizing the electrocatalytic current densities at a certain overpotential by the enzyme coverage, and taking into account that conversion between formate and CO₂ involves 2 electrons. In this way, in the case of MET-based electrocatalysis we obtain from the catalytic plateau currents (thus independent of the potential) a $k_{cat\ app}$ of 90.6 s⁻¹ and 8.6 s⁻¹ for formate oxidation and CO₂ reduction, respectively. These results confirm the bias of formate dehydrogenases towards the formate oxidation direction of their native catalytic activity measured in solution by spectrophotometry.^{6,13} In the case of the DET mechanism we obtain values of $k_{app,cat}$ (at 0.24 V overpotential relative to the thermodynamic value at the measured pH) of 20.5 s⁻¹ and 10.2 s⁻¹ for formate oxidation on Au/4-ATP and LDG/AP respectively, whereas for CO₂ reduction on LDG/AP it is 3.5 s⁻¹. In the DET mode the measured CVs reflect that the electrocatalytic currents are mostly limited by the interfacial electron transfer of the enzyme with the electrode, thus the $k_{app,cat}$ values for LDG/AP/FDH suggest an approximately 3 times faster rate in the oxidation direction than in the reduction direction. This result could be explained by a formal

redox potential of the exposed Fe₄S₄ cluster of DvFDH that is more negative than that of the formate/carbon dioxide pair.

There are several reports in the literature of FDHs immobilization on electrodes, especially for studying their ability for electrocatalytic reduction CO₂. Comparison of results is not straightforward as they involve different types of enzyme, electrodes, immobilization methods and measurement conditions (pH, temperature). Nevertheless, it is of interest to do a comparative study in the case of NADH-independent FDHs, that is both Mo- and W-FDHs, which share common characteristics and have been immobilized on electrodes by different methods. In most studies reported in the literature the metal containing FDHs have been either directly deposited on the electrode surface by adsorption,^{14,23,29-31} crosslinked with glutaraldehyde³²⁻³⁴ or entrapped within a redox polymer,^{15,35} whereas covalent bonding to the functionalized surface has seldom been studied. Higher electrocatalytic currents of CO₂ reduction are obtained with electrodes with very large electroactive areas and that allow fast mass transport of the substrate, such as carbon cloth gas-diffusion-type electrodes.^{15,33} In order to compare data in the from bioelectrodes with very different electroactive areas and enzyme loadings with those obtained in this work, it is useful to estimate their $k_{cat,app}$ values, as shown in Table S2. The $k_{cat,app}$ of 3.5 s⁻¹ we obtained for DET-based CO₂ reduction by DvH-FDH on the LDG-modified electrode is almost the same value estimated from the reported results for the same enzyme adsorbed on *meso*TiO₂,¹⁴ a mesoporous material shown to have strong and stable affinity to redox metalloenzymes while allowing fast DET. A 2-fold increase of the $k_{cat,app}$ is determined for another W-FDH crosslinked to a carbon cloth electrode coated with a conductive polymer that serves as wire for electron transfer to the enzyme.³⁴ However, the highest $k_{cat,app}$ of 91 s⁻¹ was obtained for an adsorbed monolayer of a W-FDH on a planar electrode of highly

oriented pyrolytic graphite edge, although the operational stability is very small due to continuous desorption of the enzyme, and 50% of the initial catalytic current is lost after 3.5 min of chronoamperometry.²³ In the case of MET-based systems higher $k_{cat,app}$ for CO₂ electroreduction are obtained with diffusing redox mediators in solution, such as in the present work and as reported by Kano and co-workers,³³ than with redox polymers^{15,35}, suggesting that electron hopping along the redox polymer to the redox site of entrapped enzyme could be rate-limiting the electrocatalytic process. However, the addition of redox mediators in solution is not practical for applications, and the entrapment of FDH on these redox polymers affords the highest operational stabilities reported.^{15,35}

We show in the present work that the covalent binding of *DvH*-FDH to the LDG/AP electrode allowed measuring continuous reduction of CO₂ to formate with approximately 100% faradaic yield up to two hours, although a constant decrease of the electrocatalytic current is evident. This is opposite to what we reported previously for hydrogenase covalently bound by the same strategy to carbon electrode electrodes, in which the operational stability reached up to one month with hardly any current decrease.^{26,36} Therefore, it seems that *DvH*-FDH is a more vulnerable enzyme to covalent modification, causing a lower operational stability.

5. Conclusions

The covalent binding of *DvH*-FDH to Au/4-ATP and LDG/AP electrodes modulated by electrostatic orientations allows measuring efficient DET-based bioelectrocatalysis. AFM and QCM characterization of the modified gold electrodes, as well as comparison of direct and mediated electrocatalysis, suggest that a compact layer of *DvH*-FDH is anchored to the electrode surface with some crosslinked aggregates. Immobilization of *DvH*-FDH on modified gold electrodes allows studying electrocatalytic oxidation of

formate oxidation, although it does not allow further studies of electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ because reductive desorption of the assembled thiols appears at higher potential than the thermodynamic value for reduction of CO₂. In contrast, *DvH*-FDH covalently bound to LDG electrodes modified with AP layer allows measuring high electrocatalytic currents by DET for both formate oxidation and carbon dioxide reduction, reaching values up to 700 and -200 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ respectively. Chronoamperometric measurements at -0.6 V vs SHE during 90 min led to the production of $3.7 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{M}$ formate with approximately 100 % faradaic yield. However, the operational stability was only about 90 min; crosslinking of the enzyme with glutaraldehyde improved it in about 1.5 h more but decreased the initial electrocatalytic current density.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Supporting figures S1-S8: AFM images and topographic profiles of modified electrodes; cyclic voltammograms of thiol SAMs reductive desorption and bioelectrocatalytic oxidation formate; chronoamperometries of bioelectrocatalytic oxidation formate and CO₂ reduction. Supporting tables S1 and S2: integrated chronoamperometry data and kinetic data for bioelectrocatalytic CO₂ reduction.

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Notes

The authors declare no financial competing interest.

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